

p-Nitrosodimethylaniline as a Sensitive Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium

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A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for palladium has been developed by utilising the colour reaction of palladium(II) with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline in aqueous medium. A deep brown Pd^{II}-complex is formed over a wide range of pH 0–10. The system tolerates a large excess of foreign ions. The apparent molar absorptivity of the 1 : 2 (M : R) complex is $7.7 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity is 1.4 ng cm^{-2} at 495 nm. The metal has been determined in synthetic mixtures.

NUMEROUS amines yield complexes with palladium(II) chloride, but generally colour of the products is yellow. Thus aniline and *p*-nitroaniline give yellow complexes with palladium(II) chloride¹. In contrast, the complexes of the nitrosoamines are purplish brown to bright red in colour. It appears that *p*-NO-C₆H₄-N= group is responsible for the characteristic reaction with palladium salts. Overholser and Yoe² used *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline to determine palladium by colour comparison, but no systematic work has been done regarding its analytical applications. The behaviour of the reagent towards palladium in aqueous medium has stimulated the interest of the present authors, and the colour reaction of Pd with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline has been examined systematically to develop a simple spectrophotometric method for the estimation of palladium in microgram level.

Experimental

A Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells (10 mm) were used for uv absorbance measurements. *p*-Nitrosodimethylaniline was prepared and purified³. A 0.02% ethanolic solution of the reagent was used. Palladium chloride (Johnson–Matthey) solution (1 g in 5 ml concentrated HCl) was diluted to 250 ml with distilled water and standardised gravimetrically⁴. Solution of Pd^{II} ($23.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dilution. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Sodium acetate–acetic acid buffer (pH 4.6) was used for pH adjustment.

General procedure : An appropriate amount of Pd^{II} solution (5–20 $\mu\text{g Pd}$) was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask. To it was added a 0.02% ethanolic solution (1 ml) of *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline followed by the acetate buffer (10 ml). The volume was made up with distilled water and left for 1 min to ensure complete complexation and maximum colour development. Absorbance of the solution was

measured at 495 nm against reagent blank. Amount of palladium present was computed from a calibration curve. To study the interferences, the respective foreign ions were added prior to the volume make-up.

Results and Discussion

Effect of activity and absorption spectra : Although the characteristic colour of the palladium complex developed from 2 M HCl to pH 10, the maximum colour development was found in the pH range 3–6. The reagent blank absorbs strongly at 440 nm. The palladium complex shows an absorption maxima at 495 nm with a shoulder at around 515 nm and the absorbance falls sharply thereafter (Fig. 1). Absorbance measurements against a reagent blank was carried out at 495 nm for the routine work. The pattern of the absorption spectra throughout the entire range (2 M HCl medium to pH 10) remains unchanged, indicating the formation of only one complex species in all cases.

Calibration curve : Validity of Beer's law was checked while the aqueous solution was adjusted to pH 4.6 with acetate buffer. Beer's law was found to be valid in the range 0.1–1.0 ppm of palladium. This curve shows distinct curvature at higher concentration of palladium (beyond 1 ppm). The molar absorptivity of the complex, based on palladium, was calculated to be $7.7 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and sensitivity as per Sandell's definition 1.4 ng cm^{-2} at 495 nm which classifies the colour reaction as one of the most sensitive for palladium compared with the other methods (Sandell's sensitivity, ng Pd per cm² in parenthesis) : 8-mercaptoquinoline⁵ (140), rubeanic acid⁶ (50), bismuthol-I⁵ (80), 6-carboxy-6'-hydroxy-3',5'-dichlorobenzene sulphonic acid⁶ (26), 2-methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline⁷ (15), *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-benzoylthiourea⁸ (10), morpholine-4-carbodithioate⁹ (5.7) and present method (1.4).

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of Pd^{II}-complex and reagent blank: (a) 0.47, (b) 0.31 and (c) 0.24 ppm Pd, and (d) reagent blank.

Reagent concentration: The effect of *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline concentration of the absorbance of the coloured complex was investigated keeping the other variables constant. It was found that 0.5 ml of 0.02% of the reagent was sufficient for maximum colour development of the solution containing 11.75 µg of palladium. Mole-ratio method suggested the formation of a 1 : 2 (M : R) complex.

Interference: The studies on the effect of diverse ions with 11.75 µg of palladium(II) in the final volume of 25 ml were made following the general procedure at pH 4.6 unless otherwise mentioned. Deviation of not more than ± 3% from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the system.

A 500-fold excess of Al^{III}, Be^{II}, Ba^{II}, Ce^{III}, Co^{II}, La^{III}, Pb^{II}, Mg^{II}, Sr^{II}, Th^{IV}, Zn^{II}, Zr^{IV}, U^{VI}, Ti^{II} do not interfere; 100-fold excess of Fe^{III} (in presence of citric acid) and Cu^{II} (in presence of tartrate) are tolerated. Palladium can be determined in presence of 100-fold excess of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cr^{III} if the colour development be carried out at 0.2 M HCl

medium, although the sensitivity is reduced. The presence of 0.6 mg each of Pt^{IV} and Hg^{II} and 1 mg of Rh^{III} is tolerated. Silver must be absent. Among the anions tested a 500-fold excess of phosphate, arsenate, borate, fluoride, citrate, tartrate, thiosulphate, oxalate, acetate, sulphate had no adverse effects. EDTA, however, interferes. The presence of thiocyanate, bromide, iodide give high results.

The precision and accuracy of the proposed method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of palladium. The average of six determinations of 11.75 µg Pd was found to be 11.9 µg ± 0.30 (standard deviation) with the relative mean deviation 2.4%. Thus, the method is fairly precise and reproducible. The total operation time for each run requires 10–15 min.

Analysis of synthetic mixtures: In absence of real samples, the method has been tested on a number of synthetic mixtures and the results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pd IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Sl. no.	Composition (in µg)	Pd found (µg) mean ± std. dev.
1.	Pd(11.75) + Pt(100) + Rh(100)	11.76 ± 0.30
2.	Pd(11.75) + Fe(100) + Cu(100)	11.80 ± 0.28 ^a
3.	Pd(11.75) + Ni(100) + Co(100)	11.70 ± 0.30 ^b
4.	Pd(11.75) + Mn(100) + U(100)	11.96 ± 0.26
5.	Pd(11.75) + Pt(50) + Rh(50) + Fe(50) + Cu(50)	11.76 ± 0.20 ^a
6.	Pd(11.75) + Ni(50) + Co(50) + Mo(50) + U(50)	11.80 ± 0.28 ^b

*Average of 5 determinations. ^aIn presence of citrate and tartrate. ^bIn 0.2 M HCl medium.

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